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Transverse Diagnostics: Beam Size and Emittance

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1 Introduction

Beam diagnostics is a critical component in accelerators as it provides essential information about the properties and behavior of particle beams, enabling us to monitor, control, and optimize beam performance. In our case, the particle beam will be portrayed by a laser light, and a lens used to portray the effects of a magnetic field. The goal of the experiment is to calculate the transverse emittance of our laser beam by measuring the transverse beam size.

2 Theory

2.1 Transverse Emittance

Particle beam properties in the transverse phase space are characterized by transverse beam emittance, also known as the projected phase space area. It provides a measure of the beam quality and describes the spread of particles in position and momentum space. The transverse emittance is a key parameter that determines the overall performance of an accelerator, as it quantifies the limitations imposed by the beam's size and divergence. It is often considered to assume linear behavior based on the second-order differential equation. According to Liouville's theorem, transverse emittance is conserved in linear beam optics and under linear forces. The particle in the beam moves on an ellipse in phase space. The phase space refers to a multi-dimensional space that describes the state of a particle or a beam, it comprises 6 components $(x, x', y, y', s, \delta)$. The figure below shows an example of the phase space component (x, x') , where x is the horizontal position and x' is the horizontal angle.

Figure 1: Typical ellipse representation of the first 2 components of the phase space.

Another postulate is that the ellipse shape of the phase space rotates in magnets and

shears in drift spaces, however, the total area of the phase space must be conserved under such circumstances. As can be seen from the figure below:

Figure 2: Different Phase Space with conserved area.

2.2 Emittance and Beam Matrix

Emittance itself is not directly measured but can be inferred from measurable quantities such as beam profile or beam divergence, which are projections onto the coordinate axes. These measurable quantities provide information about the spatial distribution and angle of the beam.

The Twiss parameters are often used to characterize the beam properties and exploit the transfer properties of the beam matrix allowing us to estimate and control the emittance indirectly. We assume an uncoupled motion (2D sub-space) beam matrix:

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_{11} & \Sigma_{12} \\ \Sigma_{21} & \Sigma_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \langle x^2 \rangle & \langle xx' \rangle \\ \langle xx' \rangle & \langle x'^2 \rangle \end{pmatrix} = \varepsilon \begin{pmatrix} \beta & -\alpha \\ -\alpha & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where,

$$\varepsilon = \sqrt{\det \Sigma} = \sqrt{\Sigma_{11}\Sigma_{22} - \Sigma_{12}^2} \quad (2)$$

2.3 Transport Matrix

In beam dynamics, there are similarities to linear optics. Particle beams behave similarly to laser light propagating through a medium. Transport matrices describe the effect of elements in the beam line. Quadrupole magnets act as focusing lenses in one direction, while drift spaces represent regions of free propagation, thus the transport matrix of the beam propagating in the figure below, [3](#), can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$R_{tr} = R(L_2) * R(f) * R(L_1) \quad (3)$$

The R-transport matrix is usually given as:

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} R_{11} & R_{12} \\ R_{21} & R_{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: Schematic of Experimental Setup.

Assuming that the transverse beam profile of the occupied laser does not change over a small distance (from the laser source to the lens), we can treat the total transport matrix, as it consists of a focusing lens and a drift region. This is explained in Equation 5, and shown in Figure 4.

$$R_{tr} = R(L_2) * R(f) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & L \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{f} & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{L}{f} & L \\ -\frac{1}{f} & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Figure 4: Beam Propagation

3 Measurements

3.1 Experimental setup

The experimental setup consists of 4 main components:

1. Laser Source: A visible green laser.
2. Converging Lens: with focal length $f=150\text{mm}$
3. Linear Translation Stage: To move the lens across different positions
4. Target: A screen.
5. CCD Camera: charged couple device, that takes images by converting photons into electrons.

Figure 5: Experimental Setup.

3.2 Calibration

The calibration was done by changing the screen of the target with different calibration targets such as the dot grid target and USAF 1951-target. the image from the CCD camera is acquired through an application called Pylon Viewer, we set the camera's acquisition parameters and we acquire the image. Then we rotated the images to have a correct setup. Afterward, with the modified rotated image, we used an application called ImageJ, to transfer the intensity of light in the image to a signal of intensity/pixel, this can be done by using the Analyze/Plot Profile function within the app.

3.2.1 Dot Grid Target

The concept behind this calibration is to illuminate the target screen and go through the steps mentioned previously afterward we took almost 9 points as seen in the figure below(a),

as we want to have a uniform illumination on the target to achieve better resolution. After transferring the photo to a signal, we measure the distance between two peaks (not necessarily consecutive instead the easiest peaks to measure and identify). Afterward, we transfer this distance Δx in pixel units into μ m/pixel by dividing $\frac{1000\mu m}{\Delta x}$ to obtain the camera's resolution.

Figure 6: 1st method of calibration using the dot grid target.

3.2.2 USAF 1951-target

Similarly to the previous calibration, we changed the target in this case to the USAF 1951-target which has groups of six elements each. The group numbers are at the top of the element and the element numbers at the sides of the group as can be seen from the figure below 7a, We chose groups 2-1 for our calibration as it's the most prominent element. The resolution, with respect to each group, can be calculated according to the following equation:

$$Resolution\left(\frac{linepair}{mm}\right) = 2^{Group + \frac{Element-1}{6}} \quad (6)$$

In our case, the resolution is 4 line pair/mm. Afterward, as before we transfer the intensity of the image into a signal as seen in Figure 7b, in this case, the calibration is done similarly to the dot grid target by taking the inverse of the peak-to-peak distance multiplied by 1000 μ m however this is multiplied by the resolution for each group/element.

(a) Transferred Signal

(b) Obtained Image

Figure 7: 2nd method of calibration using USAF 1951 as the target.

We have obtained a rather consistent result between the two calibrations and it appears that we have $\frac{1000\mu\text{m}}{37\text{pixel}}=27.027\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$.

3.3 Data analysis

After the calibration of the CCD camera, we can now use it for measurements and beam diagnostics. Thus we now remove the calibration targets and employ a regular screen target to take different measurements of the beam concerning different positions of our lens. The main three positions we care for are at the focal length of the lens, before the focal length, and after it. The steps of acquiring the data are similar to before, we use both pylon viewer and ImageJ, however in this case instead of the plot profile, we use the tools/curve fitting function with a Gaussian fit, as the laser has a Gaussian curve, to fit our data. From the Gaussian fit, we will be able to determine the standard deviation σ , in pixels, which will be given by the value d from our fit. We will transfer σ , into μm , using the results from our calibration.

3.3.1 At the Focal Length of the Lens

For the first acquisition, we set the lens at a distance $d=150\text{mm}$ from the target, thus the target coincides with the focal point of the lens, and we can see from the figure below that we have a well-focused beam, with $\sigma=6.96\text{ pixels}=0.1882 \times 10^3\mu\text{m}$.

(a) Gaussian Fit of the Data

(b) Obtained Image

Figure 8: The obtained image and the Gaussian fit for the data at $d=150\text{mm}$ from the target.

3.3.2 Before the Focal Length

We now move the lens farther away from the target and set it at a distance of $d=250\text{mm}$. We can see from the obtained image as well as the fit, that our beam is no longer focused and we can expect a higher standard deviation and therefore a higher emittance, which is true as $\sigma=39.82 \text{ pixels} = 1.076 \times 10^3 \mu\text{m}$.

(a) Gaussian Fit of the Data

(b) Obtained Image

Figure 9: The obtained image and the Gaussian fit for the data at $d=250\text{mm}$ from the target.

3.3.3 After the Focal Length

For the final part, we set the lens at a distance of $d=80\text{mm}$, less than the focal length of the lens. Also, it would be expected that we have a standard deviation higher than that

at the focal point which is true as we have $\sigma=33.72 \text{ pixel}=0.9115 \times 10^3 \mu\text{m}$.

(a) Gaussian Fit of the Data

(b) Obtained Image

Figure 10: The obtained image and the Gaussian fit for the data at $d=80\text{mm}$ from the target.

4 Results

The observable of this experiment is the RMS beam size - σ given by Equation 7, in relation to Equations 1 and 2.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\Sigma_{11}} \quad (7)$$

Using the transport matrix - R given by Equation 4, we can deduce the relationship between the two beam matrices, as shown below.

$$\Sigma^b = R\Sigma^a R^T \quad (8)$$

Using Equations 8, and 5, the RMS beam size at a given position can be deduced, where Σ_{11}^i , Σ_{12}^i , and Σ_{22}^i are unknowns.

$$\Sigma_{11}^f = R_{11}^2 \Sigma_{11}^i + 2R_{11}R_{12} \Sigma_{12}^i + R_{12}^2 \Sigma_{22}^i \quad (9)$$

Using indices in the transport matrix, we can modify Equation 9, into the following equation, where L_i is the measured distance between the lens and target, and σ_i is the measured RMS beam size.

$$\sigma_i^2 = \left(1 - \frac{L_i}{f}\right)^2 \Sigma_{11}^i + 2\left(1 - \frac{L_i}{f}\right)(L_i) \Sigma_{12}^i + (L_i)^2 \Sigma_{22}^i \quad (10)$$

Obtained data was tabulated as shown in Table 1. Note that, $(1 - \frac{L_i}{f})^2 = a_i$, $2(1 - \frac{L_i}{f})(L_i) = b_i$, and $(L_i)^2 = c_i$.

	Distance (L_i) (mm)	σ_i (pixel)	σ_i (μm) $\times 10^3$	a_i	b_i (mm)	c_i	σ_i^2 (μm^2)
1	155	8.07301	0.2182	0.0011	-10.3333	24025	0.0476
2	150	6.96305	0.1882	0.0000	0.0000	22500	0.0354
3	250	39.82588	1.0764	0.4444	-333.3333	62500	1.1586
4	160	7.30570	0.1975	0.0044	-21.3333	25600	0.0390
5	80	33.72530	0.9115	0.2178	74.6667	6400	0.8308
6	65	43.52516	1.1764	0.3211	73.6667	4225	1.3838
7	285	55.16484	1.4909	0.8100	-513.0000	81225	2.2229

Table 1: Obtained data by altering the distance between the lens and the target.

We need a system of three linear equations, to determine the three unknowns; Σ_{11}^i , Σ_{12}^i , and Σ_{22}^i . From the tabulated data, we used measurements 2,3, and 4 to determine the parameters. The obtained results were:

1. $\Sigma_{22}^i = 0.0016$
2. $\Sigma_{12}^i = 6.97 \times 10^{-7} m$
3. $\Sigma_{11}^i = 2.3826 \times 10^{-6} m^2$.

From these obtained values, we can deduct the transverse emittance ϵ , as follows:

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{\det \Sigma} = \sqrt{\Sigma_{11} \Sigma_{22} - \Sigma_{12}^2} = 6.1348 \times 10^{-5} m \quad (11)$$

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, from this laboratory experience, we were able to perform beam diagnostics. We successfully calibrated our CCD device, enabling accurate measurements of the beam properties. By modeling our beam with a laser source, we used a converging lens to model a quadrupole, from that we examined the physical observable, which was the root mean square (RMS) beam size. From our experimental data as well as theoretical backgrounds, we were able to calculate the transverse emittance, which is a fundamental property of

the beam, that represents the spread of particles position and momenta in the transverse direction, giving a quantitative insight of the beam's quality.